

Spatial Sampling in Mixed Reality An Overview of Ten Years of Research and Creation

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Abstract. Spatial Sampler XR is a new musical instrument linking gesture capture to sound production. In the same way that a sampler is an empty keyboard filled with sounds, Spatial Sampler XR uses gesture capture to transform the surrounding physical space into an area of keys for, recording, indexing and playing back samples. Spatial Sampler XR let the musician arrange the sound around him or her through gesture, creating a spatialized and interactive soundstage. A virtual reality headset adds to the instrument the ability to visualize the layout of sounds. The 3D immersion greatly facilitates their organization and increases the precision of the interaction. Several modes of play are possible and the interaction modalities vary according to the type of performance and the number of performers. This article first introduces the Synekine project, a 10-year research project from which the concept of spatial sampling is derived. It presents the technical devices used, the instruments created, the different modes of play in performative situations. The instrument relies on movement to link time and space. Thus, the Spatial Sampler XR is particularly suitable for movement artists as well as for extra-musical applications.

Keywords: Spatially Situated Media, Spatial Sampling, Gestural Interaction, New Musical Instrument, Gesture and Sound Processing, Interactive Performance, Movement Computing

1 Introduction

For the past ten years, through residencies and artistic creations, *the Synekine Project* has invited performers to question the intimate relationship between vocal gestures and manual gestures, through the manipulation of scenic devices based on new technologies. Metaphorically, the preeminent neuromotor link between voice and gesture is closed by “creative prostheses” joining the capture of movement to the transformation of the voice by artificial intelligence. Linking space and time through movement then transforms the search for sound into a scenic exploration.

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This paper presents the Synekine Project according to several dimensions. After the exhibition of the scientific basis and the genesis of the project, the new organology developed is described in chronological relation with the artistic works produced. Although it generates devices that can be used in other fields of application such as therapeutic rehabilitation, commercial signage or even dance and music education, these corollary results are not presented in this article for the sake of clarity of presentation.

Researches on the augmented voice in the theater [Beller11e, Beller12a, Beller14c, Beller17a] led to the instinctive, expressive and pleonastic relationship between vocality and gestural. The faculty of speaking with the hands would not only result from cultural origins, but would also result from a deep neuronal relation connecting the speech to the gestures of the hands [Iverson98]. By analogy to synesthesia, a phenomenon by which two or more senses of perception are associated, “synekinesia” would reflect our ability to associate two or more motor senses.

There is ample evidence for the ubiquitous link between manual motor and speech systems, in infant development, in deictic pointing, and in repetitive tapping and speaking tasks [Parrell14]. So, it is obvious to most people to clap their hands with every syllable spoken when we speak. Metaphorically, the Synekine Project proposes to “complete” this neuronal loop by artificially establishing an “external” link between vocal gesture and manual gesture. The voice is conventionally captured by a microphone, while the positions and dynamics of the hands are informed by different movement capture processes, which have changed from one residence to another (glove-accelerometers, Genki Wave, LeapMotion, Kinect, Optitrack and Metaquest2, see table 1.). Between the two, different computer programs based on artificial intelligence, allow the direct manipulation of sound by gesture or the learning of temporal relationships between vocal and gestural. In both cases, the result is a new organology made up of different intangible musical instruments offering the user to spread her.his voice in space, to multiply it, to segment it or to manipulate it.

Taking advantage of the instinctive nature of the voice - gesture link, and taking advantage of new technologies allowing the joint capture of the sound of the voice and the coordinates of the gesture in real time, the Synekine Project has deployed across artistic productions and residencies, a new organology of sound, invisible and intangible instruments belonging to new Human-Computer Interactions. Motivated by artistic practice, the development of this organology is presented here in a genealogical form mixing innovations and creations.

Table 1. Chronology of the works realized within the framework of the Synekine project presenting the various instruments elaborated from various technical devices.

Year	Work	Instrument	Gesture Sensor	Hand Button	Transmission	Hand tracking	Sound Recording	Visualisation
2011	Luna Park	SpokHands	XBEE V1	X	Wifi	X	Wireless headset	X
2013	Babil-on	Body Choir	XBEE V1	XBEE V1	Wifi	Kinect V1	Wireless headset	activity only
2014	TIHME	Hand Sampling, Hyper Ball, Wired Gestures, Gesture Scape, Body Choir, Sound Space	XBEE V2	XBEE V2	Wifi	Kinect V2	Wireless headset	video for gesture scape
2015	Babil-on V2	Hand Sampling, Hyper Ball, Body Choir, Sound Space	XBEE V2	XBEE V2	Wifi	Kinect V2	Wireless headset	X
2017	TEDx Paris	Body Choir	X	X	X	Kinect V2	Wireless headset	X
2016	The Memory Palace - Installation	Sound Space	X	Kinect Gesture Recognition	X	Kinect V2	Ambient mic	Projected 3D space
2016	The Memory Palace - Performance	Sound Space	XBEE V2	XBEE V2	Wifi	Kinect V2	Wireless headset	X
2017	Fissures	Hand Sampling, Body Choir, Sound Space	XBEE V2	XBEE V2	Wifi	Kinect V2	Wireless headset	X
2020	Birth of a Tree	Spatial trigger, Spatial looper, Sound Space	Genki Wave	Genki Wave	BLE	Kinect V2	Wireless headset	X
2020	Air Sampling #001	Spatial trigger, Spatial looper, Sound Space	Genki Wave	Genki Wave	BLE	Kinect V2	Static mics	X
2021	Residency UME	Spatial trigger, Spatial looper, Sound Space	OptiTrack	Genki Wave	BLE	OptiTrack	Wireless headset	X
2022	Air Sampling #002	Spatial Sampler VR	Metaquest 2	Metaquest 2	Airlink	Metaquest 2	Static mics	VR + video
2022	The Vanishing Mirror	Spatial Sampler VR	Metaquest 2	Metaquest 2	Airlink	Metaquest 2	Static mics	VR only
2023	The Fault	Spatial Sampler VR	Metaquest 2	Metaquest 2	Airlink	Metaquest 2	Static mics	VR only
2023	Air Sampling #003	Spatial Sampler VR	Metaquest 2	Metaquest 2	Airlink	Metaquest 2	Wireless headset	VR + video
2023	Macht macht macht							
2024	TBA	Spatial Sampler XR	Hololens2	Hololens2	Wifi	Hololens2	Wireless headset	XR + video

Fig. 1. Different hardware used to realize the instruments: Top left an XBEE sensor, bottom left a Genki Wave ring, top right a Kinect V2, bottom right two Optitrack cameras.

2 Genesis: Expressivity, Sensors and Luna Park

On generative models of expressivity and their applications for speech and music, an artificial intelligence algorithm based on a corpus of expressive sentences, has been used to generate an “emotional” speech, by modulating the prosody of a “neutral” utterance [Beller09a, Beller09b, Beller10]. During the development of this synthesizer of the emotion in the voice came the desire to control the prosody by the gesture. At the same time, instrumental gesture sensors were developed allowing the measurement of the dynamics of a bow by integrating small accelerometers and gyroscopes. The data related to movement is transmitted in real time by WIFI to a computer which triggers sounds and modulates effects according to the dynamics of the gesture [Bevilacqua06]. In 2010, as part of the creation of *Luna Park*¹, a musical theater work by Georges Aperghis, these sensors have been integrated into gloves and a first instrument called *SpokHands* has been developed, which literally made it possible to speak with the hands [Beller11a, b, c, d].

*SpokHands*² allows the triggering and modulation of voice samples by aerial percussion and hand elevation. Like a vocal Theremin, the instrument offers the performer the option of three-voice polyphony (her/his own and both hands) or control of text-to-speech parameters.

In this case, the natural division of a conductor's brain is used, the left brain (right hand) for the segmental part, and the right brain (left hand) for expressivity. The percussive gestures of the right-hand trigger pre-selected syllables whose pitch and intensity are modulated by continuous gestures of the left hand. A particular aerial percussion technique aimed at triggering sounds in a temporally precise manner without hurting the self has been practiced by a percussionist. Indeed, the absence of haptic feedback from a physical object could cause, in the long run, pain in the handles which acted as a stop to the percussive movement. The research work on gestural control of speech synthesis has been pursued as part of an artistic research residency at IRCAM entitled *The Synekine Project* [Beller14a].

3 *Babil-on*: From speech to time

Babil-on, for solo and electronic voice is an augmented musical theatre performance. The composition benefited from IRCAM's artistic research residency program and the piece was premiered by Richard Dubelski in Marseille, at the Théâtre des Bernardines, in 2013, as part of CMMR 2013. Like a close-up, a “Speech” character discovers his own voice, cuts it up, superimposes it, spreads it around him, multiplies it, and reveals the emotional charge intrinsic to the language. A pair of button-rings have been added to the sensor-gloves allowing for the picking and erasing of voice samples on the fly.

¹<http://www.gregbeller.com/2011/06/luna-park/>

²<http://www.gregbeller.com/2011/06/spokhands/>

Thus, *SpokHands* and the triggering of pre-made sounds evolved into *Hand Sampling*, in which the vocal flow is cut and recombined in percussive gestures.

*Hand Sampling*³ allows the performer to cut her/his voice in real time, and recombine immediately by the gesture. It involves percussive gestures that will segment and trigger vocal fragments.

The length of these fragments can vary from syllable to sentence. The order of the re-played segments can be sequential, random or palindromic, which allows different playing modes. In addition, the quality of the gesture influences the quality of the sound perceived, making the instrument expressive.

To the fast capture of the dynamics of the gesture by the accelerometer gloves has been added the relatively slow capture of the absolute position of the hands in space, by the use of depth cameras of the Kinect type [Kean2011]. This made it possible to obtain, in addition to the fine temporal precision of the percussive type triggering, the continuous control of sound processes according to the posture and the spatial position of the hands. On the other hand, the sensor brought other constraints such as a reduction in the playing area, a single performer possible, the need for a phase of calibration and detection of the skeleton, the risk of infrared disturbance by lights. The *Body Choir* uses the hand position to control a choir effect and the *Hyper Ball* to control a granular synthesizer.

Body Choir transforms a singer into a choir. This virtual choir accompanies the singer according to her/his gestures and the postures s/he adopts.

Singing involves movement of the body. This movement is captured and used to magnify the singer's musical intentions. The posture of the body and the sung note modulate in real time the harmony, the number of voices, or the spatial density of the choir.

Hyper Ball takes the form of a virtual sound ball, which the participant waters with her/his voice and modulates with her/his gesture.

The position, size and orientation of the ball influence the height, density and volume of the sound generated. This type of musical activity, by its constitution, causes choreographic movements.

In 2016 in Vancouver, Simon Fraser University, during ISEA2016, a new version Babil-on V2 has been premiered. The Kinect V2 replaced the V1 offering better acuity in capturing movement, greater flexibility of use and the possibility of following the hands of several people at the same time. Another pair of button-rings have been added to the sensor gloves.

From a compositional point of view, this second pair of button-rings offers free navigation in the structure of a work whose duration of each scene is flexible according to performer's own perception of time. From there, from the table to the stage, a change of writing paradigm takes place and we evolve in an open form that can break with the linearity of the pre-defined musical structure. Now, an improvised form can emerge from

³<http://www.gregbeller.com/2014/02/hand-sampling/>

the dynamic choices made by the performers in a situation of improvisation with these instruments.

4 *TIIME*: From time to memory:

TIIME stages three performers who play gestural, sound, visual and temporal mirror effects, in an apparent collective improvisation of which emerge from temporal themes: perception, memory, movement. The temporal relationship between vocal and manual gestures is modelled by artificial intelligence. On stage, a performer feeds a machine with his own vocal and gestural catalogue, then *Wired Gestures* restores fragments of this vocality in a way that is synchronous with the recognition and tracking of new gestures.

Wired Gestures dynamically links voice to gesture, in an artificial way. The machine simultaneously records a voice gesture and a manual gesture [Françoise2014]. It learns the temporal relationship between the two. Then it reproduces the voice, when the performer repeats the same gesture.

The nuances of timing in the gesture are then heard as prosodic variations of the voice, and it becomes possible to break down the expressivity.

Visual extension, *Gesture Scape* records jointly and categorizes voice, gesture and video. Then new gestures, either manual or vocal will activate the visual and auditory archive. Video capture is introduced as a referential element of sound time. Not only does the manual gesture reproduce the sound of the voice, it can now also reproduce the image of the performer at the time of recording. *Gesture Scape* can be seen as the visual extension of *Wired Gestures*. The performer dances with her/his double, in a dialogue made of unison and counterpoint with the past, finding her/his inspiration in the lapsus of memory.

Gesture Scape jointly records voice, gesture and video. Then, new gestures will activate this memory. The performer animates the video, by reproducing the same gesture, or by repeating the same associated sound.

The performer dances with her/his double, in a dialogue made of unison and counterpoint, inspired by lapsus of memory. From the development of these two devices, based solely on the dynamics of the gesture and not on its location, was born the desire to be able to arrange and organize it in space. Symbolically, a wave of the hand, placed above the head, to say goodbye, differs from a refusal, however expressed by the same gesture, but located below the shoulder. From a performative point of view, the staging of learners manipulating learning machines has necessarily questioned the situation of memory.

5 *The Memory Palace: From memory to the process*

Three installations and a choreographic performance, all entitled *The Memory Palace*, were created during the FACTS - Bordeaux and EXPERIMENTA - Grenoble festivals in 2017, with the support of IRCAM and ADAMI. This work cycle benefited from an artistic research residency at IDEX - University of Bordeaux, in scientific companionship with the LaBRI.

The Memory Palace is a mnemonic device practiced since antiquity allowing for memorizing long lists by arranging the elements of these in imaginary places [Yates66]. The construction of an interior architecture sensitive, has been realized with the *Sound Space*, a choreographic musical instrument linking space and time through movement. The surrounding space becomes a key zone in which the voice can be deposited and awakened by the gesture.

Sound Space is a choreographic musical instrument which links space and time, through movement. It transforms the physical space surrounding the performer, into a zone in which s.he can place her.his voice and awaken it by gesture.

By drawing her.his voice, s.he creates a unique soundstage, while evolving within it, in a creative process. The space then vibrates with a sound quality in line with the quality of movement. The *Sound Space* won the prize for technical excellence during the Guthman competition for new musical instruments.

Parable of the mnemonic, the installation transforms the place in which it is exhibited into a collective sound sculpture. Each participant is involved in the creation of a work of which s.he constitutes one of the many voices. Her.His gestures act as a reveler of the invisible sculpture. S.He can contribute to it by depositing elements of stories, sounds, or even songs that he can immediately recall in a creative process. A virtual but yet very audible forum, *The Memory Palace* acts as an indicator of the borders of the intimate, confronting the participant with the direct and immediate use of her.his voice imprint by others. In this mediation, the physical space, however empty, resonates with the different memories delivered by the participants in a temporal polyphony. Two sound installations based on the principle of *Sound Space* were presented.

The first uses a Kinect V2 for the localization and recognition of gestures, an ambient microphone as well as a video projection which materializes the sound traces of the participants on a screen. Two people were able to record sounds and play back the sounds of the others. The recording and erasing of sounds were controlled by gesture recognition (stone, leaf, scissors). The feedback showed that the main difficulty for the participants was to synchronize in order to avoid feedback (one playing while the other was recording). Finally, the representation on a 2D screen of the 3D space was a great help for the audience and made us want to use a 3D visual representation using holography or mixed reality.

The second uses the microphone and an ad hoc system of geo-localization in the confined space of mobile phones. This second version allows everyone to leave audio

messages for others by simply wandering through the space with their phone, after installing a small dedicated application.

Within the former installation, the dancer Valencia James delivers a musical choreography involving personal memories, ancestral traces and imaginary characters. The choreographic process consists of the progressive materialization of a memory palace by the deployment at different points of the stage of characters combining sound quality and quality of movement. Then, a free wandering generates by interpolation a new sound space which in turn provokes new states of the body. Everything happens as if the dancer were making an improvisation with herself and the traces of memory that she has just placed on the stage.

This dramaturgical structure in three stages (discovery of a new device; development of an ad hoc language; expression of “something else” with this language) has the capacity to attract an audience and to take it somewhere to finally surprise it there. If “the something else” refers to the discovery, the device or the elaboration of language, this linear structure resonates and loops in *mise en abyme* generating meaning. This is the case, for example, in the musical theater solo *Fissures*, in which fragments of a text on amnesia are arranged in a spatial and repetitive cut-up.

6 *Birth of a Tree: From Process to Language*

As part of a Scientiarum Musicae doctorate in the framework of the KiSS program - Kinetics in Sound and Space - at the Hochschule für Musik und Theater Hamburg, Germany, new technical gesture capture devices have been gradually being tested and integrated, such as the Genki Wave accelerometer rings, the Optitrack Motion Capture system or the Meta Quest 2 virtual reality headset. Spatial Sampling paradigm has been developed [Beller15a]. The constantly renewed interest in the device *Sound Space* in different artistic configurations stems from its adaptability. Indeed, it is an empty and silent box at the start, just like the musical sampler. So other instruments were derived from the hybridization of these two concepts and tested in the creation of *Birth of a Tree*. They are the basis of the creative improvisation process of the *Air Sampling* series.

Air Sampling is a series of improvised performances in which a sound source is sampled and distributed in space in real time. In the first performance #001, the sound source is given by Lin Chen on percussion and vocals. The author, playing the *Sound Space*, *Spatial Trigger* and *Spatial Looper* instruments, records and plays the samples in space. They perform with the percussionist an improvised musical choreography of which percussions are the only acoustic source.

In the 1970s, the sampler revolutionized music production. This electronic music instrument, whose memory is empty at the beginning, allows the musician to create her/his own universe from percussion samples, ensembles, groups of instruments or orchestras and can also serve as a platform for musical creation.

The paradigm of the *Spatial Sampler* is to substitute the midi keyboard which classically indexes the samples, with spatial coordinates describing the positions of the hands.

Spatial Trigger allows the automatic segmentation of a sound and its distribution in space by the gesture, then the selection of one of these fragments according to its position and its triggering by aerial percussion.

The *Spatial Looper* allows the mixing of several sound loops according to the proximity of the hands, as well as the generation of music from the fragments distributed in space.

Many musicians are now familiar with the "looper" or live looping. One of the main difficulties in this art is dealing with multiple layers of samples (usually dealt with a guitar pedal). The *Spatial Looper* transforms the space surrounding the performer into a spatial sequencer and makes it easier to not only access the different layers but also to remember them.

7 *Air Sampling: From Language To 3D Sculpture*

For Air Sampling #002, still using the percussion sounds played by Lin Chen, VR versions of the Sound Space, Spatial Trigger and Spatial Looper instruments were created and tested in a performance situation. An OpenGL representation allows the performer to visualize the position of the recorded sounds in a Meta Quest 2 headset, which greatly facilitates the organization of the session and allows for greater spatio-temporal accuracy.

The graphical representation of the recorded sounds also offers the possibility to draw 3D structures in the virtual space. The other performers and the audience can see the structure emerging from the gestures through video projection. Several performance situations have been explored with or without sharing the representation of the structure with the audience through video projection. Making it visible facilitates the understanding of the instrument by the audience but unbalances the performance if other musicians contribute. The other musicians only show the scores and their interpretation choices in front of them through the sound produced. In Vanishing Mirror, the performer is the only one to visualize the recording of the sounds produced by a piano-cello-vocal trio. Different modes of interaction with the sound sources have been explored, from the duet with a percussionist in AirSampling #002, to the live sampling of an ensemble of seven instruments in The Fault (see Figure 2).

While Virtual Reality allows for a better organization of the sounds recorded and produced, it has the unfortunate side effect of visually cutting the performer off from the other musicians as well as the audience. Not only does it reduce the facial expression of the performer whose eyes are no longer visible, but the rupture of the visual contact of the performer with the others can generate complex situations for the synchronization in a improvisation situation. In AirSampling #003 - Macht macht, the strolling public interacts with the performer, who has a microphone. A protocol must then be established

between the participating visitor and the performer in order to synchronize the production of sound on the one hand with the gesture of the other.

The total obstruction of the visual contact in situation of improvisation can cause an interesting situation of performance, but can also harm the connivance between the public, the musicians and the performer made "blind". As holographic video is not yet mature enough, mixed reality seems to be the way to reduce the loss of visual contact. The evolution of the Spatial Sampler VR to the Spatial Sampler XR is currently being developed with the HoloLens 2 mixed reality technology. This evolution implies the substitution of controllers by gesture recognition, thus reducing the playability of the instrument by decreasing its response time. Apart from the Optitrack system which operates at 120 frames per second, the other systems based on video or depth sensors do not offer a small enough latency to allow aerial percussion (latency lower than 20ms). Just as we added acceleration sensors to the data from the Kinect, the fusion of gesture recognition data with data from on-board accelerometers (Xbee sensors or Genki Wave rings) is being considered to improve gameplay in mixed reality.

Fig. 2. The *Fault*, Opera composed by the g. Beller, 2023, Hamburg, Germany. In the background, a representation of a 3D sculpture elaborated from the sounds of the instrumentalists.

8 Conclusion

The nexialist approach of *the Synekine Project* aims to establish protocols that generate creative processes in a holistic approach mixing Arts and Sciences. The path oscillates between meetings with scientific researchers, technical development phases, experimentation residencies of new scenic devices and crystallization of performative situations in shows or installations.

This article relates 10 years of research and artistic production accompanied by technological development. In chronological form, it exposes the development of the research theme of spatial sampling, the new musical instruments elaborated through the evolution of the technologies of gesture capture as well as the artistic stakes approached in different works. From the link between gesture and voice, the research has evolved towards the manipulation of spatially situated media. From Hand Sampling or spatial sampler to sound space, different instruments make movement the link between time and space. The technical developments are based on the evolution of technologies for capturing gestures. The fusion of data from the capture of the dynamics of the gesture, the position of the hands in the space and the sound, allows the elaboration of an interactive sound scene. In performance, improvisation, comprovisation or composition situations, different modes of play are presented. The creation of about fifteen works with these instruments gives a context to the artistic stakes of spatial sampling.

Virtual reality allows to represent and manipulate "sounds located in space" in an environment comparable to that of a 3D painting software. The custom arrangement of media whose recording and playback is done on the fly inaugurates the possibility of "spatially situated media" editing. Compared to modern sequencers whose organization of windows and sounds is constrained by 2D, the possibility of freely organizing media content in 3D space seems to accelerate the work of the editor, who joins spatial memory to content memory. The use of the memory palace in the audio-visual editing activity can greatly facilitate the access to the contents and accelerate the work steps without requiring any particular cognitive dispositions of the user.

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References

- [Beller09a] Beller, Grégory (2009). Analyse et Modèle Génératif de l'Expressivité: application à la parole et à l'interprétation musicale », Paris 6 – IRCAM
- [Beller09b] Beller, Grégory (2009). Transformation of Expressivity in Speech », The Role of Prosody in the Expression of Emotions in English and in French, ed. Peter Lang. (Peter Lang)

- [Beller10] Beller, Grégory (2010). *Expresso: Transformation of Expressivity in Speech*, Speech Prosody, Chicago
- [Beller11a] Beller, Grégory, Aperghis, Georges (2011). *Contrôle gestuel de la synthèse concaténative en temps réel dans Luna Park: rapport recherche*
- [Beller11b] Beller, Grégory, Aperghis, Georges (2011). *Gestural Control of Real-Time Concatenative Synthesis in Luna Park* », P3S, International Workshop on Performative Speech and Singing Synthesis, Vancouver, pp. 23-28
- [Beller11c] Beller, Grégory (2011). *Gestural Control Of Real Time Concatenative Synthesis*, ICPhS, Hong Kong
- [Beller11d] Beller, Grégory (2011). *Gestural Control of Real-Time Speech Synthesis in Luna Park*, SMC, Padova
- [Beller11e] Beller, Grégory (2011). *Arcane d'Un mage en été*, Théâtre Public, n° 200
- [Beller12a] Beller, Grégory (2012). *In-vivo: laboratoire de recherche et d'expérimentation autour du son pour le théâtre*, Towards a History of Sound in Theatre, Montreal
- [Beller14a] Beller, Grégory (2014). *The Synekine Project*», MOCO 2014, IRCAM, Paris
- [Kean2011] Kean, S., Hall, J.C., Perry, P. (2011). *Microsoft's Kinect SDK*. In: *Meet the Kinect*. Apress. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4302-3889-8_8
- [Françoise2014] Jules Françoise, Norbert Schnell, Riccardo Borghesi, Frédéric Bevilacqua. *Probabilistic Models for Designing Motion and Sound Relationships*. *Proceedings of the 2014 International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression*, Jun 2014, London, UK, United Kingdom. pp.287-292. (hal-01061335)
- [Beller14c], Beller, Grégory (2014). *L'IRCAM et la voix augmentée au théâtre: Les nouvelles technologies sonores au service de la dramaturgie*, L'Annuaire théâtral, Numéro 56-57, p. 195-205
- [Beller15a], Beller, Grégory (2015). *Sound Space and Spatial Sampler*, MOCO 2015, SFU, Vancouver
- [Beller17a], Beller, Grégory (2017). *Spectacle vivant: des voix imaginaires aux monstres vocaux*, InaGlobal, Paris, France
- [Bevilacqua06] Bevilacqua Frederic, Rasamimanana Nicolas, Fléty Emmanuel, Lemouton Serge, Baschet Florence (2006). *The augmented violin project: research, composition and performance report*. In *6th International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME 06)*, Paris
- [Iverson98] Iverson Jana M. & Goldin-Meadow Susan (1998). *Why people gesture when they speak*, Nature 396, 228
- [Laukka13], Laukka, Petri, Eerola, Tuomas, Thingujam, Nutankumar S., Yamasaki, Teruo, Beller, Grégory (2013). *Universal and Culture-Specific Factors in the Recognition and Performance of Musical Affect Expressions*, Emotion, American Psychological Association, Vol 13(3), 434-449
- [Parrell14] Benjamin Parrell, Louis Goldstein, Sungbok Lee, Dani Byrd (2014). *Spatiotemporal coupling between speech and manual motor actions*. *Journal of Phonetics*, Volume 42, Pages 1-11